

THE IMPORTANCE OF ORGANIZING LEGAL UPBRINGING IN OUR COUNTRY

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the issues of the essence, meaning and main directions of the legal upbringing organization which is one of the most relevant at the present stage. Life and human rights in a state governed by the rule of law, considered as the highest value, are explained by the meaning of legal literacy and legal culture. The importance of legal upbringing is expressed in the formation of respect for the law, the rights, its value and the need for unconditional execution.

Keywords: legal culture, legal education, legal relations, personality, public property, legal upbringing, legal agitation, legal practice, legality, law and order.

Law as a social phenomenon reflects the satisfactory or unsatisfactory relations of people. While people in any public relations have different legal thinking and concepts, legal regulation also has a different form. If people express their attitude to the past law, the law in the present and the law in the future, then these relations rise to the level of rational, filled with reasonable emotions. At the present stage, one of the important problems for us is not only attention to legal upbringing, but also its education and training. Along with the difficulties, our people are experiencing political tension in the age of space technology, so the role of upbringing and instilling legal upbringing in building a new Kazakhstan requires special necessity. As indicated in subparagraph 5 of Article 12 of the Constitution of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the absence of an indication of public morality requires attention to the importance of legal upbringing[1]. The object of our research is the social relations regulating upbringing in society. The main purpose is to clarify the concept and special features of legal upbringing. The upbringing of law sets itself the noble tasks of forming a child's personality, instilling in him a high ideological attitude and attitude to public property. Much attention is paid by the state to legal literacy and legal upbringing, but it cannot be said that this problem has been fully solved. One of the aspects of citizens' abstinence in obtaining legal knowledge and mastering legal upbringing is the lack of a practical mechanism necessary for the wide dissemination of legal thought. Legal upbringing is the transfer of legal methods and ideas of legal culture and resolution of tension in society by one generation to the younger generation. The concept of legal upbringing can be interpreted in a broad and narrow sense of the word. Legal upbringing forms a purposeful and organized, systemic consciousness, instilling personal legal awareness into a person's life. A test of upbringing is being conducted, systematizing the culture of citizens' rights.

For the proper organization of legal upbringing, first of all, it is important to understand what legal upbringing is. It should be noted that the concept of "legal upbringing" does not have a general term. Someone understands legal upbringing as legal knowledge and forms this knowledge as necessary for training. Others understand that legal upbringing is respect for the law, the rights, as well as the ability to comply with legal

norms. Third, in legal education, the purposeful activity of the educator forms in future generations certain attitudes, needs and requirements, value orientations and superstructures of order. Nevertheless, legal upbringing should be considered as an effective and comprehensive process, the content of which is legal education.

But it is not only to enrich the educator's knowledge of law, rights and legal activity, but also to influence the consciousness of the person being brought up, designed for self-improvement of a person in accordance with legal norms.

An important part of legal upbringing is the formation of respect for the law, the rights, explaining its value and the need for unconditional execution. The relevance of this aspect of legal upbringing in order to form the rule of law is that respect for the law is a valuable addition to every person.

As Sukhomlinsky wrote: "education becomes a creation generated by man only when young hearts are subdued by ardent feelings."

"Patriotism" is one of the most important and valuable things of society and the state in all spheres of life, which is a spiritual achievement of an individual, manifested in demonstrating a high level of its development and vigorous activity for the country.

In a broad sense, the education of the environment has a greater influence on a person than the influence of legal education, and if we talk about the fact that the legal service of executive state bodies and officials has its own influence, although it does not seek to give legal education to people, then in the narrow sense of this words he shows that they are directly aimed at improving the legal culture of the people, taking over the entire society as a whole. Legal upbringing is very closely related to legal education, that is, upbringing cannot be without education, and education necessarily has an effective impact on upbringing. Here it is necessary to distinguish spheres of influence through several differences, where upbringing shows people emotional freedom, worldview, appreciation, and education gives an informational and cognitive impact on a person. This means the connection of legal upbringing with public consciousness. Legal upbringing is an activity directed by a state body and society in order to form the legal consciousness and legal culture of citizens and officials.

Legal upbringing is a complex process consisting of the following components:

- subjects of upbringing (state bodies, civil servants, politicians, teachers, journalists, etc.);
- objects of upbringing (citizens, labor collectives, social groups, etc.);
- the content of upbringing (reflection of people's attitude to legal and political values, ideas, principles, information, experience, etc.);
- upbringing methods (persuasion, encouragement, punishment and other psychological and pedagogical methods of influencing educational objects);
- upbringing models (forms).

1) legal education (acquisition of legal knowledge in schools, secondary special and higher educational institutions);

2) legal propaganda (provides for the dissemination of legal ideas and legal requirements among the population through television, radio, and other mass media);

3) legal practice (primarily promotes the dissemination of legal information and knowledge through the participation of citizens in the process of law enforcement activities);

4) self-education (related to self-analysis of legal phenomena, self-study, personal skills);

Legal upbringing cannot be limited to legal information of citizens. This is a very deep process related to the provisions of the Constitution and the existing fundamental laws, human and civil rights and freedoms.

The legal culture of a person is the knowledge and understanding of laws, as well as the compliance of actions with them. The legal culture of the individual is closely connected with legal consciousness and leads to it. But it is wider than legal consciousness or includes not only its psychological and ideological elements, but also behavior that has legal significance[2].

This is one of the main areas of legal upbringing of the school, family and society - it opens a wide way for the prevention of delinquency among students.

Our state has always attached great importance to the upbringing of young people. The formation of deep respect for the laws of Kazakhstan, their unconditional observance and implementation is the result of many years of upbringing work. In most cases, a misunderstanding of what material and spiritual goods are, within the framework of legal consciousness, causes antisocial behavior. That is why the task of legal upbringing is to convey legal norms to the consciousness of each student, not only to convey them, but also to fight for their everyday behavior.

The upbringing base of law begins with the family.

Measures to prevent violations of the rule of law among future generations:

- elimination of the situation that contributes to the formation of bad behavior of the violator;
- improvement of upbringing, living conditions and environment of the student;
- effective organization of educational and labor activities;
- carrying out educational work on the defense of

the motherland, strengthening the power of the native country, freedom of speech and the press;

There is no doubt that one aspect of legal upbringing has to do with sex education. To marry a loved one, start a family, give birth to and take care of a child, help children in case of separation - all these are laws and obligations that young people must understand. Today's student is tomorrow's specialist, head of production, manager. Therefore, after graduating from a vocational school, he needs a profession as well as legal upbringing. The Russian teacher K. D. Ushinsky, who scientifically formulated the national position of pedagogy and upbringing, said: "There is no upbringing system that is equally suitable for all people, both in life and in science. The national upbringing system of each nation is different. It is impossible to introduce the upbringing system of another country into your own country, because people have a different model of life and model of upbringing. Also, along with general upbringing, attention should be paid to legal upbringing. Where do we place in a child a sense of right, equality and justice?"

There are gaps in the organization of legal upbringing work among rural youth, it is necessary to implement the measures established by higher organizations on the issue of propaganda and legal upbringing among young people, to increase the responsibility of workers.

The education of the law is based on the methods of justice, which teach to follow the right path. In such a situation, a person turns to his self-respect.[3;71] A student may underestimate the people around him, social benefits. This alone often causes him to break a lot of legal upbringing. Talking about legal issues and bringing them to the audience is a very difficult art. It is not enough to be educated, but it is important to be an experienced teacher who has seen a lot and is able to find the key to people's hearts. The life of students at school and university is the most important stage in the formation of personality. During these years, morals, worldview, beliefs, collectivity, organization, exactingness to oneself and others, honesty and sincerity, goodwill and restraint, energy and courage are formed. Their content includes respect for state laws and the peculiarities of life in society, intolerance for violations of social laws, and the maintenance of public order. Legal culture is considered from two positions:

- students' knowledge of legal issues, legal relations, activities of legal institutions.
- the influence of the pedagogical and psychological significance of the individual on legal consciousness.

Human legal culture is complex. When it comes to a person, his mind, behavior many questions arise. A legal society based on democratic principles ensures the full and free realization of the creative forces, intentions, games, feelings, aspirations of each person. The improvement of democracy is directly dependent on the creation of the legal foundations of state and public life. The process of establishing the legal foundations for the life of the state and society requires the implementation of the following important measures:

- continuous improvement of laws - confirmation of the implementation of the law;
- participation of each citizen in the establishment of public order;

It follows from this that it is necessary to take care of the establishment of law and order directly on the shoulders of the state. There is a close connection between the general culture of a person and his legal culture [4; 102]. That is why we consider legal upbringing as an integral part of the theory of moral upbringing. During the period of social reconstruction, the shortcomings of law are overcome in the process of culture formation. Law embraces the entire life of society and every member of society. A person with a low level of legal culture pays attention to the law only in case of gross violation of the law and does not notice many cases when the requirements of the law are not recognized [5; 64]. serious lack of legal culture. Ignorance of the law, its violation does not save from responsibility. At the same time, the student should not confuse the concepts of law and legal culture. Legal culture requires comprehensive legal knowledge from the student. The legal culture of a person is a complex psychological phenomenon that manifests itself in many important areas of the life of society and the state. One of the most important means of education that contributes to the formation of the qualitative qualities of a moral personality is the appropriate discipline and a high level of character education.

Thus, the legal culture of a person is a deep unity of proper behavior, respect for the law with a comprehensive knowledge of the law, protection of the law.

If we consider the conscious order and behavior as the basis of law and culture, then it is directly related to artistic culture at the level of relationships and feelings. The world of the senses plays a key role in aesthetic relationships. Literature and art influence us with their artistic images, which we perceive through our senses. With the help of art, especially through literature, we learn about the world and social relations.

A person who has risen to these two levels of legal culture, that is, a person who knows the law and respects the law, avoids actions that are contrary to the law. Only the ability to follow the law will appear. This is called obedience to the law. At this level, the internal driving force is shame, the human conscience. Shame, conscience, and convictions are connected not only with keeping the law, but also with the willingness to participate in constant vigorous actions to protect the law.

Observance of law, a sense of justice, duty, responsibility, legality is a manifestation of a person's personality from above [6; 47]. From this it is not difficult to understand that the sense of legality is the composition of legal culture.

At the present stage, the gradual democratic development of society requires from the teaching community high skill and creativity in the

implementation of legal education as in general secondary schools, colleges, universities.

In order for education to meet modern legal requirements, it is necessary, first of all, to study deeply the best practices of classroom teachers and schools, to find optimal forms, methods and techniques, rationally, generically using their results in educational and upbringing work.

In conclusion, legal upbringing is a system of principles and norms aimed at the formation of legal ideas that reflect the value of world and national legal culture. The purpose of legal upbringing is to improve the personality, considered as the highest legal culture, qualitatively stabilized qualities and habits, concretized by social tasks, provided with the necessary law and order, legal awareness and legal knowledge. The formation of high responsibility and respect for the laws of the state is also one of the main directions of legal upbringing. Legal upbringing and legal consciousness begin first with the family. Life shows that for the development of modern society, each of us must respect the rule of law and temper our sense of justice and strength. In order to prevent types of crimes, it is necessary to strengthen legal propaganda and further improve legal upbringing. The rule of law has formed the legal basis of civil society. All its spheres are based on it: socio-cultural, economic and political. Accordingly, it becomes the legal basis of the entire state reality. Also, the basis for the formation and development of the rule of law and civil society begins with the ability to rationally organize and implement the mechanism of this legal upbringing and legal education. This, in turn, is very important for the strength of the foundation of our state.

References

1. Constitution of The Republic of Kazakhstan. 1995.- https://adilet.zan.kz/kaz/docs/K950001000_
2. Akimova T.I. Pravovaia propaganda kak sposob formirovaniia pozitivnykh elementov pravovogo soznaniia, opredeliaushchikh pokazatel loialnosti pravosoznaniia. – Elektronnaia versiia na: "#_ftnref1" name="_ftn1" title="">>[1] Pochtar T.M. Pravovoe vospitanie v pedagogicheskikh vuzakh: voprosy metodologii i metodiki: Diss. : kand. iurid. nauk. M., - 2001 r.
3. Absattarov R.B. Vospitanie kazakhstanskogo naroda: voprosy teorii i praktiki // Aktualnye voprosy obshchestvennoi zhizni. Sbornik statei. –Almaty,1994. –С.71.
4. Pevtsova E. A. Pravovoe vospitanie kak sredstvo formirovaniia pravovoi kultury // Sovremennoe pravo. - 2003. - № 8.
5. A. Q. Spanov, U. Şapaq. Qūqyqtyq tǎrtıp pen zañdylyqtyñ özara bailanysy. Zañger 2009. №4. –Б.64-66
6. Kenjalın J. Ūlt ruhyn ūlyqtaǵan ūrpaqpyz. – Almaty, 2005. – 46-47 better.